

Ran Spaces and Holonomy

Ryan J. Buchanan

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Let M be a flat (i.e., zero curvature) compact manifold, and let p_x be a basepoint. Define a curve $\gamma : p_x \rightarrow p_x$ such that $\gamma(0) = p_x$ and $\gamma(1) = p_x$ but $\gamma(c) = p_y \forall c \in]0, 1[\forall y \neq x$. Define the *holonomy representation* by:

$$\mathcal{H}_\gamma : \pi_1(M, p) \rightarrow \text{Aut}(E_p) \quad (0.1)$$

where E is the fiber over p . This immediately necessitates the notion of a *holonomy bundle* of the fiber, which we will set to be:

$$\mathcal{H}_E = \bigcup_i E_{p_i} \quad (0.2)$$

Set

$$X_\mu = E_{p_j} \ominus E_{p_i} \sim E_{p_{j-i}} \quad (0.3)$$

and define a torsion-free connection ∇_X on M satisfying

$$\nabla_X L_m = -L_n \nabla_X \quad (0.4)$$

At this point, we can drop our ruse and let p be a particle:

$$p = (\sigma, \tau)m \quad (0.5)$$

Then, we have:

$$\delta_{m-n,0} \cdot p = Cr_p \quad (0.6)$$

as our creation operator, and we can inductively define $Cr_p^{-1} : p \rightarrow |\emptyset\rangle$ as the annihilation operator. The L_i are the generators of our *Virasoro algebra*, which plays a significant role in conformal field theory (CFT) by controlling the dynamics of the primary field(s) and their descendants.

1 Levi-Civita Field

If our theory is smooth, and the manifold is not nullhomotopic, then we essentially obtain an infinite number of degrees of freedom. This is modelled by a topological realization of the Levi-Civita field; specifically, we have an element ε satisfying:

- $\forall n \in \mathbb{R} \quad \varepsilon < n$
- $\forall n \in \mathbb{R} \quad \varepsilon^{-m} > n \quad m \geq 1$
- $\forall m, n > 0 \quad \varepsilon^n < \varepsilon^m \quad m < n$

- $\forall m, n > 0 \quad \varepsilon^{-m} < \varepsilon^{-n} \quad m < n$

The Levi-Civita field is written $\mathcal{R}$, or $\mathbb{R}[\varepsilon]$. Clearly, this is no good, as it screws up a lot of equations. So, construct a sequence:

$$\mathcal{R} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}_{Fin} \longrightarrow LocSys(\mathbb{R}) \quad (1.1)$$

beginning with the Levi-Civita field and ending with a real local system.

The values $r \in LocSys(\mathbb{R}) = \sqrt{\sigma + \tau}$ are the *observables* of the theory, and the values $r_{pre} \in \mathcal{R}$ are the *unknowables*; they are what we *want* to compute, but do not have the computational power or energy to do so.¹ In my earlier thinking with Hancock, we considered a sort of “absolute reference frame” which acted as the pullback for all of the slices of spacetime; now, I want to rewrite this as:

$$\mathcal{A} \cong \lim_{n \rightarrow \varepsilon} g^n \curvearrowright (\mathbb{A}_{Minkowski}^{3+1}) \quad (1.2)$$

where g is a profinite action in an extension of the Poincaré group. Actually, it would be better to express this as

$$\mathcal{A}_{Ran} \cong \pi_{n \rightarrow \infty}(\mathbb{A}_{Minkowski}^{3+1}) + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \pi_n(P_\mu) \quad (1.3)$$

$$\pi_{Ran(A)}(F) + \pi_{Ran(n)}(P_\mu) \quad (1.4)$$

where A is an arbitrary ring (not necessarily finite), $Ran(n) = \langle n \rangle = 0, \dots, n$ and P_μ is the canonical spacetime translation of Ferrara [1].

Actually, we can rewrite our original bundle as:

$$\mathcal{H}_E = E_{p_{Ran(i)}} \quad (1.5)$$

and the $\mathcal{H}_\gamma$ term becomes the class from $\mathcal{A}_{Ran}$ to Minkowski spacetime. We can then pass to local systems; the following diagram:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} & \mathcal{A}_{Ran} & \\ \swarrow \text{---} & & \searrow \text{---} \\ LocSys(\mathbb{R}P^3) & \longleftarrow & \mathbb{A}_{Minkowski}^{3+1} \end{array}$$

summarizes the situation at hand, where $dim_{\mathbb{C}}(\mathbb{R}P^3) = 2$.

2 Stringy Dynamics

It was proven by Tao [3] that flat quasicohherent sheaves on the infinitesimal Ran space are trivial; i.e.:

$$Ran_{inf}^n \xrightleftharpoons[q]{p} Spec k =: \mathbf{pt} \quad (2.1)$$

This suffices to show that only the leading order terms contribute significantly; i.e., survive the pullback to $\mathcal{A}_{Ran}$. This can be interpreted by imagining a stress tensor $T(\mathbf{b} \pm r)$ acting strongest

¹If we *were* able to perform such a computation, it would a.) require an infinite amount of resources and b.) perfectly predict and retrodict everything in the causal history of the entire spacetime.

on homotopies which are infinitesimally near to some “privileged” reference frame. This frame is the F we used in equation (1.4), though in the past we have also denoted it by $\square$. We have:

$$\square^\pm = T(\mathfrak{b} \pm r) \quad (2.2)$$

satisfying

$$\square^+ \square^- = -\frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} \square^+ \quad (2.3)$$

where $\mathcal{N} = 2^q$ for q a small prime ($q \leq 7$) is the number of supersymmetries. For the gravitational theory, we have $p = 3$, but in the absence of gravity we set $p = p_{min} = 2$. We can think of q (as Haefliger did) as the *codimension* of a foliation $\mathcal{F}_{\mathbb{S}^2 \times \mathbb{R}}$ on the spacetime manifold. Physically, this is a partitioning of a string’s worldtube into *sectors*; we have:

$$\mathcal{F}_{\mathbb{S}^2 \times \mathbb{R}} = \bigvee_{\lambda} \phi_{\lambda} \quad (2.4)$$

where ϕ is the physical field, and λ satisfies the relationships:

$$\lambda \square^\pm = \frac{1}{p} \mp \square \quad (2.5)$$

and

$$\lambda^2(\square^\pm) = (\lambda \square^\pm)^2 \quad (2.6)$$

Summarizing the equation (2.3), we obtain the following diagram:

$$\square^- \longleftarrow \square \xrightarrow{\Psi} \square^+$$

where $\Psi = \begin{bmatrix} \psi_- \\ \psi_+ \end{bmatrix}$ is a bi-spinor, satisfying

$$\Psi \circ \psi_{\bullet} = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} T(\mathcal{O}_{\mathfrak{b}}) \quad (2.7)$$

so that applying when applied after any map $\psi_{\bullet} \square \rightarrow \square^\pm$, we obtain a damped value for observable of the field.

2.1 Privileged Frames

Up until now, we have not formally defined what a “privileged frame” is. We will remedy this here.

Definition 2.1. *A privileged frame is a site defined of the universal spacetime manifold such that all quasicoherent sheaves defined on the frame are locally coherent.*

When we work in the category $Priv_F$ of privileged frames, we essentially stipulate that all mathematical structures behave as close to classical as possible. This requirement ensures that traditional equations of motion interact seamlessly with our observables, allowing us to apply familiar physical intuitions and results. By confining ourselves to privileged frames, we maximize the coherence of the sheaves and the predictability of our mathematical constructs, creating an environment where the underlying physical theories can be expressed clearly and effectively.

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & & [F] \\
 & \nearrow^{Emb(F)} & \Downarrow^{S \rightarrow S_{Classical}} \\
 LocSys(F) & \longleftrightarrow & Priv_F
 \end{array}$$

A References

- [1] S. Ferrara, *Supertheories*, (1988)
- [2] R.J. Buchanan, *Galois Connections on a Brane*, (2023)
- [3] J. Tao, *n-excisive functors, canonical connections, and line bundles on the Ran space*, (2010)